

VISUAL IDENTITY GUIDELINES

November 2020

The logo symbol is based on a spatial principle, to hint at abstract geographical locations (of the 7 main partner cities) in relation to each other.

The result is a dynamic swirl that represents connectivity, co-learning and co-production between the partner cities in both Latin America and Europe. This is shown as a continuous cycle where ideas flow freely in both directions between all partners and feed into the project ecosystem.

The logo – components

The Conexus logo is made up of three main components; the **symbol**, the **logotype** and the **strapline**.

When using the full logo they should always be used in the proportions, spacing and alignment as shown (left). This ensures the brand is represented with visual consistency across all media.

CONEXUS or Conexus?

The official project name registered with the European Commission is CONEXUS, with all uppercase letters. This can look too strong when used in some contexts or when repeated in a text. When needed you can use the name Conexus in title case.

Recommendation:

Use CONEXUS for headings or when writing the project name on its own, for example, in a diagram. Use Conexus when you repeat the name several times in body text or when you follow the name with the word project i.e. Conexus project.

Please note that the logo should always be implemented from approved sources.

Digital files in a variety of file formats can be downloaded here:

conexusnbs.com/brand

NO STRAPLINE

Five individual logo variations have been created – the difference being the representations of the project strapline.

WITH STRAPLINE TRILINGUAL

It is recommended the trilingual version is used whenever all partners are involved on co-learning/co-production. Or a wider reach is required across English/Spanish/Portuguese-speaking countries and partner cities.

ENGLISH

A single strapline version has also been created for use on more specific outputs in the three respective languages.

ESPAÑOL

The no strapline version is for use whenever the logo needs to appear smaller. This may be the case when included as a logo amongst others, for example; in a project partner block. This can also be utilised when the project strapline(s) are being used prominently elsewhere on the design/layout.

PORTUGUÊS

More explanation of this follows on the 'Recommended reproduction size' page.

NO STRAPLINE

WITH STRAPLINE

The preference is to represent the logo in full colour whenever possible.

A version using the 90% black 'logotype' colour has been created for single-colour use.

A reversed or (white-out) version has been created for cases where the logo may need to appear over a strong background colour or image.

Whenever applying the reversed (white-out) logo over an image, extra care should be taken to ensure the CONEXUS logotype and strapline(s) remain clear and readable.

To retain maximum clarity and readability, guidance is set out below on the minimum recommended reproduction sizes of the **no strapline** logo and **with strapline** logos.

NO STRAPLINE

Minimum recommended height in print = 10mm

Use of the **no strapline** logo should be no smaller than 10mm high when printed and no smaller than 70px high when displayed on screen.

WITH STRAPLINE

Optimum recommended height in print = 20mm or greater

The optimum size of the **with strapline** logos should be 20mm high or greater (where space allows) when printed and 100px or greater when displayed on screen.

This ensures the trilingual or single language strapline(s) retain a degree of readability.

Recommended clear space

Height of 'C' from 'CONEXUS' in the logotype is used to calculate the clear space.
Grey surround indicates minimum recommended clear space.

To ensure the logo is free from any other visual distraction a minimum amount of space should be maintained around it. This visually separates it from any other graphic elements and typography. This distance is called 'clear space'.

The minimum clear space should be the height of the 'C' from the logotype, as shown in the diagram (left).

Whenever possible this amount of clear space can be increased for further clarity.

Logo colour references – PRIMARY COLOURS

Breakdown values for the primary brand colours, which are derived from the logo symbol and logotype are detailed here.

For further flexibility – the recommended tints (10% • 30% • 60%) can be used to good effect for more subtle representations or visual hierarchy in design and layout.

No attempt to change these colours or their values should be made to the logo files.

Brand colours – SECONDARY PALETTE

					60%	30%	10%

A secondary palette has also been developed to work well alongside the primary brand colours used in the logo.

It is recommended that these are used sparingly. Best use cases for these are likely to be accompanying graphics such as; diagrams, tables and project branded infographics. Should a design or layout require the use of colour-coding these can also implemented.

For further flexibility – the recommended tints (10% • 30% • 60%) can be used to good effect for more subtle representations or visual hierarchy in design and layout.

Urbane Rounded

Thin

Demi Bold

Extra Light

Bold

Light

Heavy

Medium

AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLlMmNn

OoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz

£ ? ! @ / £ \$ € + () , . ; : ' " - - © ® ™ *

0123456789 Urbane Rounded Light

Typography is an important component of the visual identity and when used consistently it unifies the appearance of every piece of Conexus communication.

The official typeface of Conexus is **Urbane Rounded**. The logotype and straplines are set in this typeface. It should be used whenever possible, particularly on any materials intended for professional print output.

Different weights and sizes can be utilised for varying emphasis and visual hierarchy.

Nunito

Extra Light	<i>Italic</i>
Light	<i>Italic</i>
Regular	<i>Italic</i>
Semi Bold	<i>Italic</i>
Bold	<i>Italic</i>

AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLlMmNn

OoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz

& ? ! @ / £ \$ € + () , . ; : ‘ “ - — © ® ™ *

0123456789 Nunito Light

fonts.google.com/specimen/Nunito

A font called **Nunito** has been selected from the free and open source GoogleFonts library.

This compliments the look and feel of the logotype used in the logo.

It can be used for both digital and print outputs when the Urbane Rounded font is not available or purchasing is cost-prohibitive.

Further explanation of suggested usage is detailed on the next page...

Visit GoogleFonts using the link and download the free/open source font files by clicking on the 'Download family' button.

Unarchive and install the font files on to your local system.

SAMPLE HEADING IN NUNITO BOLD (24PT)

Sample sub-head in Nunito Semi Bold (16pt)

An example of running body copy in Nunito Regular (11pt)

Atiust perntae endendebitas soloribus qui nobit et exerest atia voluptas *endusan isinven tibusandion* por sit quia volupta tquodit periossit reptaeputdam, ut odit, tet, soluptae dolor sam.

Sample sub-head in Nunito Semi Bold (16pt)

Uptaturi tecae qui conse cus, cum fugia nullore rest audae la cor a nectatis nonet **venimus ipsam vellorem fugia** antus a nonsequamus, ipsandi que comnisquam fugia volores ectatent que etus imuscim

eria que etuscimus que reperum rescia nonseque debis doles non pre quia nim ium ea volum quuntotatem aut peruntusam, que sectibea dellessi untist voluptis modi aut ad minus moluptatet fugitio rporibus, id que

liquos repudist eaquunt volutenectem quas molupti sus nos resecum dolores sequas mo ipsantia cuptatatendi reribus daecero exerspe llatur, sit vellesed errore nonsedi piciae voluptat.

Sample pull-out in Nunito Semi Bold (16pt)

Sample text set in the GoogleFont **Nunito**.

This gives a visual guide on suggested styling of how the various weights and brand colours could be used.

Sample sub-head in Nunito Semi Bold (16pt)

- Sample bullet point
- Sample bullet point, this one runs over more than one line to show variation
- Sample bullet point
- Sample bullet point, this one runs over more than one line to show variation
- Sample bullet point, this one runs over more than one line to show variation

Arial

Regular

Regular Italic

Bold

Bold Italic

AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLlMmNn

OoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz

& ? ! @ / £ \$ € + () , . ; : ‘ “ - – © ® ™ *

0123456789 Arial Regular

The Microsoft templates – Word (report) and PowerPoint (slide presentation) utilise the standard system font **Arial**.

This was a decision made to ensure immediate use of templates would be an easy process with no foreseeable issues when sharing templates between partners working on different platforms or legacy versions of software.

Any dissemination of results or communications activity must acknowledge the support received from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. In accordance with the European Commission's guidance, the European emblem shall be a minimum height of 10mm and used in conjunction with text acknowledging funding from the European Union.

Conexus will comply with the European Commission's visual identity guidance as outlined in: The use of the EU emblem in the context of EU programmes: Guidelines for beneficiaries and other third parties.

ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/use-emblem_en.pdf

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 867564

Digital logo and template files can be downloaded here:

conexusnbs.com/brand

CONEXUS

Urban nature connects us
Conectados por la naturaleza urbana
Conectados pela natureza urbana

conexusnbs.com